

DEVELOPMENT OF MEDIA COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS IN THE ENVIRONMENT OF MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract.

This in the article modern information technologies in the environment of students media competence development of the Internet young to generation bringing benefit and damages about of psychologists opinion , media advertising damages about word is conducted

Key words.

information and communication technologies of students spiritual and physical health , morality _ norms , thinking

Introduction

As you know , education society in development important role he plays _ _ How in the field no matter how high to knowledge have specialists scientific research developments with engage in , new product types Create and technologies development opportunity have will be

In the world globalization processes and companies between there is deep competition environment experts too extraordinary that's it ready to be Demand is enough They are not only own ideas development and created theoretical models in practice current reach for comfortable conditions they provide , that's it with together with the economy innovative development for too important intellectual factor is considered Many publications , public information tools , information communication technologies media that named all things too much except a lot use , mostly in cases , modern school of students spiritual and physical to health negative effect is showing .

Main Part

Psychologists It is said that it is wide scattered coming media technologies useful it's not and significant level take risks . _ _ The majority According to studies , the computer _ games , entertainment with games _ _ _ _ _ programs , public information of means effect under school of students _ short term thinking is

formed . For example , energy drinks advertising let's take Supposedly , this drinks strength devotee to the effect have that advertising will be done . Whole in the world this the drink consumption of the doers most of them teenager young people organize does it is Here it is that's it advertising mainly under the influence of a teenager young people , still organism full forming before , this drinks from the norm more than consumption to do and in consequence his from harm dead the ones that are too observation can _ Media in the world different different Internet sites and social networks through went towards promote being carried out national to tradition and to our traditions and ethics norms , in general , correct not coming Film and clips our youth to his mind negative effect showing the family said holy of concepts to decay reason is happening Of this due to critical mind level decreases , material and moral value in the system surroundings the world acceptance to do as well as data analysis and synthesis to do in ability changes face gives _

Psychological and pedagogical of research as shown , short term thinking based on around universe scattered evidence mosaic becomes _ This to the situation school of students emotional scope by learning remains , evidence kaleidoscope like one after another exchange and school to his students regularly respectively new impressions need will be Such fast in progress school of students emotional of the field sensitivity decrease starts _ Short term thinking the owner only known in length in meanings works and optional complicated semiotic structures with work ca n't External from the side this school of students long time during each how information attention towards can't and his analysis to do ability in the decrease manifestation will be Short term thinking computer tools and public information tools through long lifetime during mosaic and ready in the form of low level superficial information consumption to do through work is issued .

Results And Discussions

Short term thinking is often minute _ feelings thinking that is called To the child known one situation understanding for 2-3 minutes is given and that's it immediately all of them unity need will be because new data flow begins . Short term in thought feeling and responsibility of feelings weakening happen will be Think about it this appearance of the child complete development interrupt will give and his personality fundamentally to the violation take will come Such in the circumstances media competence develop , his modern requirements account received without formation and pedagogical conditions determination need _ now scientific and technical development requirements suitable without student of young people information technologies regarding knowledge improvement

through media competence formation and development directions designation it is necessary

LS Vygotsky of children the first 2 years until speech development stage as characterizes . Two from the age after thinking and speech directions in cooperation develop starts and this of the process synergy observed . AA Nemirech , O. V. Barsukova and another series of psychologists a lot yearly studies public _ _ information tools , computer games and heart key programs active consumption to do status adults by to control not available and education standards requirements answer does not give This while school students psychic development normal to pass destruction gives _ In the end , speech thinking own in place does not develop because , public shows to see and computer games to play in the process school students internal and external from speech they do n't use So , social to networks appeal doing to teenagers , eng first of all , to young people from the internet use teaching culture (media culture). need _

School students modern information tools using literate communication to do is important and valuable information separate qualifications to teach necessity appear will be Unfortunately , in our country school of students to media literacy enough attention not given That's it therefore of media education current to be done separately current important have _ Media education of our people traditions , national values relied on without , universal to values based on organize to be done need _ Media education our youth with modern media safe and efficient communication to do prepares , in them media awareness , media literacy , media culture and media competence forms . Media our children in upbringing , education to give and cultural in development big place occuppies , as well as the public his opinion in formation and management in processes active participation is enough Modern school students are usually adults _ more public information tools and computer from the equipment in use to advantages have will be , media innovations absorb , media experience and strictly media to the contests owners _

Conclusion

Modern school education institutions public information tools , interactive technologies , remote education shape and education get , electronic the arts fast respectively come in is going School students always grow up going information to the streams face they come and their own search qualifications demonstration do , taken information independent respectively critical evaluation in the process big difficulties from the head they forgive Such in the circumstances specialists in preparation of the media role much increases . This own in turn from the teacher high erudition , great creative , scientific potential and initiative Demand because it

does the third a thousand annually work market strong competition and economic need environment conditions personnel to choose separately attention giving them _ serious is being sorted . That's why for school students to media literacy teaching our country education in politics priority direction to be need _ After all , it is our nation The future is modern _ school of students to media literacy depends will be

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